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Bibliometric study of the Ph.D. theses in Library and Information science of Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow

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Abstract

The study covers 28 Ph.D. theses submitted during 1995-2018. The study identified that 2016 was the most productive year and the contribution of male research scholars is more as compared to female research scholars. Prof. K. L. Mahawar has supervised the maximum number of theses i.e. 14 corresponding to 50% of all. Majority of references are single authored and from journals. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) is the most cited journal. Development and Information Seeking Behavior is the most studied sub domain of LIS. Bibliometric studies on PhD theses has been conducted in various countries in various disciplines, but the study of the published literature shows that a very few attempts have been made in India so far that too in Library and Information Science domain. The study determines the bibliographic features and could be an asset to researchers, academicians and librarians.

Keywords: Bibliometric study; Citations analysis; Library and Information Science literature; Theses; References; Authorship pattern; Research trend; Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Central University, India.

1. Introduction

Research and development is a continuous process and it indicates the advancements in a particular discipline or field. Bibliometrics techniques allow us to analyze the academic literature published in a particular domain of knowledge as they quantify the process of written communication. The present study is an attempt to quantify the research activity of library and information science domain through the PhD theses in Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow.

2. Review of literature

The concept of bibliometrics originated as statistical bibliography as Prichered (1969) defined it as, “the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media of communication” and now has developed into a major field, “allowing us to determine the variety of scientific indicators, evaluating the scientific output, selecting journals for libraries and even the forecasting of potential Nobel Laurates” (Zafrunnisha, 2012). The bibliometric techniques are quantitative and Zafrunnisha (2012) observed that bibliometric techniques are mostly used to determine trends in literature in Library and Information Science research. In Sri Lanka, Dilani (2015) argues that librarians can respond to the research demands of students by analysing bibliographic citations in theses. In the words of Alemna (2016), “Academics all over the world place emphasis on research and publications, not only because research enriches the teaching and learning process as well as contributing to the body of knowledge, but also because it is a major determinant of institutional prestige” .

The review of literature of the bibliometric conducted on the doctoral theses in LIS domain:

Pandita and Singh (2017) revealed Gujarat being the most productive state and that Dr. M. K. Prajapati supervised the maximum theses. Chaman Sab (2016) highlighted 2002 as the most productive year. Dr. Karisiddappa C R was regarded as the most prolific research guide. The same finding was given by Singh (2015) along with state wise, Karnataka, the major contributor, and institution wise, Jiwaji University Gwalior topping the list and 1993/1995 were the most affective years. Chikate and Patil (2008) studied the 6257 citations in 27 theses. Majority of citations were of journals, books, web resources, reference books, and conference proceedings. The College and Research Libraries was the most cited journal and US as 1076 citations were of the journals published from US. The maximum citations were of the single author literature with majority of citations in English (2,485) and only 118 citations in Marathi language. Ghai (2001) showed the highly productive authors; applicability of the Lotka’s Law; and the more solo contributions than the collaborative. Study further identified the Indian journals are cited the most while the USA and the UK stands at second and third respectively. He has further drawn the attention towards the inter-disciplinary nature of the studies and proved that the citations reveal the trend to cite recent material that is not older than 19 years.

3. Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study can be summarized as:

1. To identify year-wise distribution of doctoral theses.
2. To explore supervisor wise distribution of doctoral theses.
3. To know gender-wise distribution of doctoral theses.
4. To explore author-wise distribution of references.
5. To recognize the most cited journals on the basis of references.
6. To identify the distribution of references on the basis of type of cited source materials.
7. To determine the distribution of Theses on the basis of Sub-disciplines of LIS.

4. Methodology

Twenty Eight Ph.D. theses of Library and Information sciences submitted to the Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow during the period 2008 to 2018 were selected as the primary data. All the references from the 28 theses were noted down on a data sheet to collect the relevant data and information accurately for different bibliometric features. The theses were categorized on the basis of Year of submission, Supervisor, gender of the Research Scholar and sub domain of LIS studied, and on the other hand references were categorized to identify the authorship pattern, most cited journals and most cited form of information sources i.e. books, journals articles, newspapers, reports, conference proceedings, interviews, theses/dissertations etc. The data was analyzed and interpreted on MS Excel 2010.

5. Analysis

5.1 Year-wise Distribution of Doctoral Theses

The Table- 5.1 shows the year-wise distribution of 28 doctoral theses submitted to the Department of Library and Information Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow during the period 2008 to 2018. The highest number of theses was submitted in the year 2016 (9 Theses, 32.1%) followed by the year 2017 (5 Theses, 17.8%).

Table- 5.1 Year-wise Distribution of Doctoral Theses

S. No.	Year	No. of Theses	Percentage
1	2008	1	3.5%
2	2010	1	3.5%
3	2011	3	10.7%
4	2014	2	7.1%
5	2015	4	14.2%
6	2016	9	32.1%
7	2017	5	17.8%
8	2018	3	10.7%
	Total	28	100%

5.2 Supervisor/Guide-wise Distribution of Doctoral Theses

The Table- 5.2 shows the Supervisor-wise distribution of theses and the most prolific supervisor in the Department of Library and Information Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow. The table depicts that Prof. K. L. Mahawar supervised the maximum 14 theses (50%) followed by Prof. M. P. Singh with 8 theses (28.58%).

Table -5.2 Supervisors - wise Distributions of Doctoral Theses

S. No.	Name of Supervisor	No. of Theses	Percentage
1	Prof. K. L. Mahawar	14	50%
2	Prof. M. P. Singh	8	28.58%
3	Prof. Shilpi Verma	2	7.14%
4	Dr. S. K. Sonkar	2	7.14%
5	Dr. R. K. Choudhary	2	7.14%
	Total	28	100%

5.3 Gender-wise Distribution of Authors of Doctoral Theses

The Table-5.3 shows the gender wise distribution of authors in 28 doctoral theses. Male research scholars submitted the most, with 16 theses (57.14%) while female research scholars submitted 12 theses (42.86%) during the period of 2008 to 2018 for the award of the degree of Ph.D in Library and Information Science.

Table- 5.3 Gender-wise Distribution of Authors

S. No.	Gender	No. of Theses	Percentage
1	Male	16	57.14%
2	Female	12	42.86%
	Total	28	100%

5.4 Author-wise Distribution of References in Doctoral Theses

Table- 5.4 shows the author-wise distribution of references listed after each chapter in the theses given in all 28 theses submitted by the research scholars during 2008-2018. For 28 theses total 3490 references could be identified for the various categories of authorship. Total single author sources are 1964 (56.27%), which is highest in authorship pattern. Total two author sources are 963 (27.59%), three author sources are 302 (8.65%), more than three author sources are 144 (4.12%) and corporate author sources are 117 (3.35%).

Table-5.4 Author-wise Distribution of References

S. No.	Authorship Pattern	No. of References	Percentage
1	Single Author	1964	56.27%
2	Two Author	963	27.59%
3	Three Author	302	8.65%
4	More than Three Author	144	4.12%
5	Corporate Author	117	3.35%
	Total	3490	100%

5.5 Most Cited Journals on the basis of References in the Doctoral Theses

The Table- 5.5 represents the top 10 most cited journals by the authors of all 28 submitted theses on the basis of references listed at the end of chapters in the theses.

Table- 5.5 Top 10 Most Cited and Core Journals on the basis of references

S. No.	Rank	Journal Name	No. of Citations
1	1	Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)	127
2	2	Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS)	75
3	3	DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology	65
4	4	The Electronic Library	50
5	5	Journal of Documentation	35
6	6	College & Research Libraries	34
7	7	Library Trends	30
8	8	SRELS Journal of Information Management	27
9	8	Library Hi-Tech	27
10	9	Library Herald	26
11	10	The Journal of Academic Librarianship	25

The above table shows that Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) ranked 1st (with 127 citations) as the most cited journal, then, Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS) grabbed 2nd rank with 75 citations, DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology secured 3rd rank with 65 citations, 4th rank goes to The Electronic Library with 50 citations and 5th rank achieved by Journal of Documentation with 35 citations.

5.6 Distribution of References on the basis of Cited Source Material

The table- 5.6 identifies the top 10 type of sources cited for references listed at the end of chapters in the theses.

Table- 5.6 Distribution of References on the basis of Cited Source Material

S. No.	Source Type	No. of Citations
1	Journal	1967
2	Website	993
3	Book	775
4	Conference Proceeding	288
5	Theses	80
6	Report	75
7	Encyclopaedia	27
8	Magazine	25
9	Dissertation	23
10	Dictionary	20

The above table- 5.6 shows that Journal is the most cited source type with 1967 citations, followed by Websites with 993 citations, Book with 775 citations, Conference Proceeding with 288 citations and theses with 80 citations.

5.7 Distribution of Theses on the basis of Sub-disciplines of LIS

It is always interesting to know the distribution of articles published in a subject in their sub-disciplines. This informs us about the current ‘hot topics’ for research as well as bring to our notice those subject areas which are lagging behind and where more research is needed. Table- 5.7 depicts the numbers of theses dealing with each sub-domain of LIS studied at the Department of Library and Information Science, Baba Saheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University.

Table- 5.7 Distribution of Theses on the basis of Sub-disciplines of LIS

S. No.	Sub-discipline	No. of Theses
1	Collection Development	4
2	Information Seeking Behaviour	4
3	Library Management	3
4	Library Resources	3
5	Library Software	2
6	Library Profession	2

7	User Studies	2
8	Bibliometrics	1
9	Conservation and Preservation	1
10	Digital Library	1
11	Information Communication Technology	1
12	Library Services	1
13	Library Survey	1
14	Public Library	1
15	Special Libraries	1
	Total	28

The Table- 5.7 shows that from total 28 theses submitted 4 theses each were on Collection Development and Information Seeking Behaviour and 3 each on Library Management and Library Resources followed by 2 each on Library Software, Library Profession and User Studies.

Findings and Conclusion

The study identified the bibliometric features for the 28 theses submitted during the period 2008-2018 in the Department of Library and Information Science of Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow. As per the study, 2016 was identified as the most productive year with 09 theses submissions and male research scholars outnumber female research scholars in the submission of theses. Prof. K. L. Mahawar has supervised the maximum number of theses i.e. 14 corresponding to 50% of all the theses. Majority of references are single authored and from journals. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) is the most cited journal with 127 citations, then, Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS) grabbed 2nd rank with 75 citations, followed by DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology on 3rd rank with 65 citations and The Electronic Library with 50 citations is ranked 4th. Collection Development and Information Seeking Behavior is the most studied sub domain of LIS. The study draws the attention of the research professionals and academicians in LIS towards the need to study the conservation And Presevation practices in Indian Libraries, India's initiative towards digitization of libraries, online presence of libraries and services, bibliometrics, scientometrics, webometrics, and new domains like altmetrics and surveys on different libraries to study the social media penetration, MOOCs etc. The study will be beneficial to understand the research trend at the DLIS, BBAU, Lucknow, a central university under the Ministry of Human Resource and Development, Government of India.

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